

GEOHERMAL PLAY TYPES IN THE AFAR TRIANGLE (ETHIOPIA, ERITREA, DJIBOUTI)

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ABSTRACT

The LEAP-RE project engaged the Geothermal Atlas Project a global approach to geothermal resources in Africa (GAA WP9). In this context, Varet (2022) proposed to distinguish ten geothermal play-types based on their geodynamic context. The Afar triangle (extending over Ethiopia, Eritrea, and Djibouti) certainly deserve a specific approach as it appear as the most promising geothermal region of the continent. This, due to its unique situation with two oceanic ridges (Red Sea and Gulf of Aden, 2cm/y) with the Main Ethiopian Rift (MER) northern extremity and most active part (6 to 8 mm/y) of the EARS. As a consequence, a large variety of geothermal play types are present, which we propose to identify, subdivide and synthetise in 9 play-types as follows:

1. The faulted plateau margins (FPM), where hot-springs occur along marginal grabens and transverse faults. These a-magmatic systems allowing for local development of Direct Use or even medium enthalpy applications with electricity production from ORCs.
2. The leaky transverse fracture zones (LTFZ) affecting the faulted margins of the Nuban Plateau and Danakil block (Arrata). Large central volcanoes, eventually with calderas and silicic peralkaline products, produced ideal conditions for large electricity production with Ma'Alalta and Bidu-Dubbi (Ethio-Eritrea border, Varet, 2020) as typical examples.
3. The immediate margins of active oceanic rift (AORM) penetrating the continent as observed in Djibouti along the Gulf of Tadjourah both N and S margins. Several sites where normal faults and transverse fractures cross each other allow to connect with the sub-oceanic ridge, thermal emergences indicating high temperature geothermal systems.
4. The active axial volcanic ranges (AAVR), dominantly basaltic, where recurrent diking allow to maintain high temperature heat sources: Asal, Manda Inakir, Manda Harraro, Alayta, Tat'Ali and Erta Ale. Within these ranges, specific sites allow for the development of high temperature reservoirs. Even the extremities of these ranges, in a sedimentary context, allow for active hydrothermal sites of high geothermal interest.
5. This is notably the case in the leaky transform fault zones (LTFZ) – between two axial ranges (spreading segments) - where magma differentiation at shallow depth allow for the development of silicic units and promising large size geothermal systems.
6. In Southern Afar, along the MER Axis (SAMA), 7 central volcanoes display series of differentiated products, including ignimbrites, calderas, and associated hydrothermal systems potentially suitable for large-size High Temperature geothermal developments.
7. Along the Afar floor, active faults (AFAF) affecting the stratoid series (3 to 1 My) in areas of tectonic stress between steading segments allow for local energy and water production systems based on exploitation of steam surface upwelling.
8. A rather specific geothermal play type is found near the Ethio-Djibouti border, with Dama Ale shield volcano, built at the intersection between the Red Sea – Aden rift (Tendaho-Gobaad rift segment, WNW-ESE) and the MER (NNE-SSW) at the extremity of the Awash Valley endoreic basin (ending at Lake Abhé)

1. INTRODUCTION

The accreting plate margins, mainly located along the Mid-Oceanic Ridges (MOR) are known to be the place of high convective heat flow due to the uprise of the low velocity asthenosphere through a thinned lithosphere. A shallow magma chamber, a few Km deep only, also characterize the active ridge axis. These characteristics are found in sub-oceanic environment – i.e. inaccessible for economic geothermal development - except in Iceland and in Afar, where similar conditions are found on land, with similar spreading rate of 2 cm/y measured. A specificity of Afar is that this oceanic spreading occurs within a continent, with elevated plateaux all around, where active faulting also occur, with frequent thermal convective hydrothermal system are found. Another characteristic is the presence, in southern Afar, of the Main Ethiopian Rift axis, northern extremity of the East African Rift System (EARS), a continental rift type characterized – as all along the Eastern branch of EARS – by the alternance of central silicic volcanoes frequently, rift in rift faulted floor (Fig.1).

Fig.1: Tectonic setting of the Afar depression (modified after Keir et al., 2011, 2013). Solid black lines show Oligocene–Miocene border faults of the Red Sea, Gulf of Aden, and Main Ethiopian Rift. Red segments show the Quaternary–Recent subaerial rift axes, and green triangles show Holocene volcanoes. Dashed lines show the Tendaho–Goba’ad Discontinuity (TGD). The Arrata microplate is shaded yellow. Gray circles show large earthquakes during 1973–2012 sourced from the National Earthquake Information Centre (NEIC) catalog. Earthquake focal mechanisms are from the Global Centroid Moment Tensor (CMT) catalogue. Top left inset: topography of NE Africa and Arabia. Gray arrows show plate motions relative to a fixed Nubian plate (ArRajehi et al., 2010). Bottom right inset: zoom of Oligocene–Miocene border faults (black) and Quaternary–Recent subaerial rift axes (red lines) with arrows showing motion of the Arrata microplate (McClusky et al., 2010).

2. FPM: FAULTED PLATEAU MARGINS

Hot-springs occur along the foot of both Nubian and Somalian plateaus escarpment along marginal grabens and transverse faults (Fig.2). These a-magmatic systems allow for Direct Use or even medium enthalpy applications with electricity production from ORCs.

Fig.2: Topographic map of Afar derived from ASTER data (90 m resolution). (b) Sections A-A' and B-B', illustrating the difference in structural style between (A-A') the Western Afar Margin (WAM) and (B-B') the Southern Afar Margin (SAM). The former is dominated by antithetic faulting (towards the plateau) and associated marginal grabens, whereas the latter is characterized by synthetic (basinward) faulting. Section locations are indicated in (a). Both systems allow for thermal upflows. Orange dots indicate historic earthquakes from the 1970–2018 NEIC earthquake catalog. Focal mechanisms are derived from the CMT catalog. AB: Aisha Block, DB: Danakil Block. DD: Danakil Depression, DS: Dabbahu segment, TGD: Tendaho–Gobaad discontinuity. After Zwaan et al. (2020)

Fig.3 (Left): satellite image showing the location of the main hot-springs along the eastern flank of the Shewa Robit - Kombolchia grabens as well as the high temperature hydrothermal sites in the nearby Southern Afar depression (middle Awash basin). The orientation of these graben is NNE-SSW (Main Ethiopian Rift) to the south and NNW-SSE (Red Sea) to the north. Observe the limit of the Nubian plateau: on the right (west) the Nile hydrographic basin, on the left (East) the Afar depression and the Awash River basin. The Addis Ababa – Makale road is passing along these graben floor at a medium altitude (1300-1500 m) between the plateau (2500-3000 m) and the Afar depression (600-400m). Location of major hot-springs in yellow; nearest fumaroles sites in Afar in red. (Right): geological interpretative section of the corresponding hydrogeological system feeding the hot-springs in the marginal graben and Southern Afar volcanic ranges (J.Varet, 2018)

At least 4 hydrothermal sites are identified, listed in Table 1, between Shewa Robit and Kombolcha, all located in wetlands. Exploiting such sites tapping hydrothermal convective circulations along these eastern border faults of the escarpment provides opportunities for direct uses projects.

Name	Location N	Location E	Altitude	Temperature
<u>Shewa Robit</u>	09° 59'37	39° 52'54	1.301m	51,6°C
<u>Borkena</u>	10° 38'06	39° 55'22	1.403m	72,0°C
<u>Shekla</u>	10° 48'14	39° 49'25	1.437m	52,0°C
<u>Harbu</u>	10° 55'53	39° 48'32	1.566m	72,0°C

Table 1: main hot-springs identified in the marginal grabens along the Nubian escarpment NE from Debre Birhan (130 Km from Addis Abeba), between Debre Sina (190 Km from AA) and Dessie (401 Km from Addis Ababa).

All along the Nubian escarpment several hot-spring sites are observed, offering opportunities for local geothermal developments (Fig.4).

Fig.4: warm springs at Erepti graben, northern Afar, emerging form down-faulted jurassic limestions, reaching 76°C with abundant carbonate travertine deposits; mainly used for providing drinking water for herds (Photos J.Varet).

Similar low to medium temperature sites emerging from the normal faults bounding the Afar SE margin are found along the foot of the Somalian plateau escarpment. At Arabi, Somalian Regional state of Ethiopia, geothermal exploration was engaged by the Geological Survey of Ethiopia (Wondifra et al., 2022) and considered for development by a Canadian company.

3. LTFZ: LEAKY TRANSVERSE FRACTURE ZONES

Affecting the faulted margins of the Nubian Plateau and Danakil block (Arrata), in areas of discontinuities marked by transverse fracture zones (TFZ), large central volcanoes, producing silicic peralkaline products, frequently from calderas (Barberi et al. 1970, 1972, 1974), produced ideal conditions for large electricity production, with Ma'Alalta and Bidu-Dubbi as typical examples (Fig.5). The Bidu-Dubbi volcanic system marks the southern extremity of the Arrata Block extending across the Ethiopia-Eritrea border with Nabro volcano producing a Plinian eruption in 2011 (Varet, 2018, 2020).

Fig.5 Left: Microplate interpretation of the Afar active volcano-tectonic and hydrothermal manifestations (Barberi & Varet, 1977) showing the Bidu (Bi) -Dubbi (Di) transverse (NE-SW) alignment. The motion of the Arabia plate with respect to Nubia (2 cm/y) is pictured with the red arrow. A major transverse fault zone (TFZ) linking Hanish Islands (HI), to Dabbayra (Da) transverse volcanic unit (also marking, as for Ma'Alalta (MA), offset of the Nubian basement) through Dubbi (Di), Bidu (Bi) and Dabbahu (Du). Axial ranges, axis of spreading in grey. Anticlockwise rotation of the Arrata block with progressive dying of the Red Sea spreading axis and increase of spreading rates within Afar southwards. It also induces an increasing "leaking" from SW to NE along the Bidu-Dubbi TFZ, directly reflected in the volcanology : increasing basaltic activity towards the Red Sea. (From Varet, 2018). Right: Geological map of the Ma'Alalta (MA) and Bidu-Dubbi, (from CNR-CNRS map 1973). Pre-Miocene basement (pale brown), polychromatic detrital unit (brown), recent basalts (blue) and rhyolitic pyroclasts (orange).

Fig.6: Model of the magma plumbing system beneath Nabro (Hamling et al., 2014). (A) Map view of the subsidence from InSAR data. Black outlines: caldera rim and lava flow. Red dashed line: vent region. Black dots: relocated hypocenters. Yellow rectangle: NE-SW thrust fault outline. (B) Three-dimensional view with the observed subsidence draped on topography.: hypocenter locations at depth. Red: earthquakes induced by the eruption. Black: regional earthquakes induced by changes to the stress field. Proposed source (dark red spot), conduit (large black arrow), thrust fault (grey plane), and potential magma supply system (small black arrow) are also highlighted.

Geophysical records of the Nabro 2011 eruption (Fig.6) allowed to picture the magmatic reservoir and fault-controlled surface manifestations, displaying the typical characteristics of the caldera-hosted high temperature geothermal systems.

4. AORM: ACTIVE OCEANIC RIFT MARGINS

The immediate active oceanic rift margins (AORM) penetrating the continent as observed in Djibouti along both the N and S margins of the Gulf of Tadjourah reveals a specific geothermal play type. As observed in Fig.1 and 2., the Gulf of Tadjourah appears as a particularly active axis with a narrow succession of spreading segments and TFZ. Several sites are found along the coast where normal faults and transverse fractures cross each other allowing for direct hydrothermal connections with the sub-oceanic ridge (Fig.7), with thermal emergences indicating high temperature geothermal systems (Haga et al. 2012; Houmed et al., 2012).

Fig.7: Example of the Obock geothermal system. Left: Interpretative scheme of the major determinants: heat source located along the WNW-ESE axial volcanic rift zones of the oceanic floor (double red arrows), and the NE-SW transform faults (orange discontinuous lines) that are equally leaky. Major sites of hydrothermal surface manifestations (red bordered black) and visible faults at the surface along the coastline (red). Middle: thermal emission site along faulted coral reefs coast lines. Right: Conceptual model proposed for the Obock with ICDP deep well (in red) & geothermal exploration well in black. The Mabla rhyolites (marron) and overlying Dalha basalts (green), intensively faulted and eroded, are covered by the younger basalts (1 to 3 My) emitted at the initial stage of the gulf opening. The geothermal reservoir (up to 220°C) is expected to develop at a depth of 1000 to 2000m in the fractured quaternary detrital formations. Deeper supercritical fluids are expected to be met at 3000 to 4000m depth while approaching the spreading axis under the sea floor

5. AAVR: ACTIVE AXIAL VOLCANIC RANGES

These dominantly basaltic ranges, where recurrent diking allow to maintain high temperature heat sources: Asal, Manda Inakir, Manda Harraro, Alayta, Tat'Ali and Erta Ale (Barberi & Varet, 1975, 1977) are places where the accreting magma reach speeds up to 2 cm/y, and where therefore the highest heat flow conditions are found. Within these ranges, specific sites allow for the development of high temperature reservoirs. Even the extremities of these ranges, in a sedimentary context, allow for active hydrothermal sites of high geothermal interest.

For Erta Ale range (Fig.8; Barberi & Varet 1970) such favourable conditions are found north where several silicic centres developed, and south where diking and faulting are particularly active. Along this axis, north, the salt plain shows numerous occurrences of thermal manifestations and phreatic explosion craters, revealing the presence of a geothermal reservoir underneath the salt deposits and other sedimentary layers.

Fig.8: The Erta Ale range located in its northern Afar geological context, extracted from the geological map at 1/500.000 scale (CNR-CNRS Afar team, 1973). Whereas the faulted pre-Mesozoic basement, the polychrome tertiary detritic series and the coral reefs of the former Danakil sea (yellow) are visible on both sides, the lava sequence of Erta Ale is made of olivine basalts (blue), andesine basalts and ferrobasalts (violet) dark trachytes (pink), and silicic trachytes and rhyolites (yellow) in the most evolved volcanic units (northern part of the range). The corresponding magmatic evolution is summarized in the alkali-silica diagram. Photos are the Erta Ale lava lake and the rims of a phreatic explosion crater in the salt plain north (Barberi et al. 1973; Barberi & Varet, 1970).

SE from Erta Ale range, the Tat'Ali range (Fig.9) display all the characteristics of an axial range with dominantly basaltic flows emitted from a shield elongated NNW-SSE topped by an axial graben from which differentiated products – up to peralkaline rhyolites were emitted. Several fumaroles emission sites are observed along this axis. To the south, active tectonics produced the Harak graben with a floor 120m below sea level, surrounded by normally faulted blocks on both sides Varet & Gardo, 2020). Along the axis of this graben, open fissures induced the formation of spectacular mud volcanoes and steam vents, with temperatures reaching 115°C, attesting the presence of a high temperature geothermal system extending along this active rift axis underneath the sedimentary cover despite the lack of recent volcanic products at the surface.

Fig.9: The active Tat'Ali volcanic range and its southern extension with the geothermally active Harak Graben. Geological map, left, with the location of the Harak site (red rectangle), seen on Satellite image. Two examples of the numerous mud volcanoes are shown right (Photo J.Varet).

Within the AAVR play type, Asal in Djibouti is the only site which was investigated for geothermal, including deep exploration wells (French Geological Survey in the 70th, Italian Aid in the 80th, and lastly a World Bank initiative in 2014-2016 (Fig.10). Despite a promising geodynamic environment, with a typical accreting axis with a symmetrical active volcanic rift (with the Ardoukoba eruption in 1978), these successive attempts, did not allow for economic development. This due to the cooling of the geothermal reservoir after the opening of the rift axis inducing cold sea water inflow towards Lake Asal, - 154m bsl, (Varet, 2014).

Fig.10: Left: The active volcanic axis of the Asal rift (red arrow) with the active fault along which an important ground sea water flow cross through from Ghoubbet to lake Asal (blue arrow). Drilled sites (in green, numbered) and main fumaroles (in red). The red square show the WB exploration drilling (2015-2016). Centre: Temperature profiles measured in the Asal wells A3 to A5. Note the inversion of temperature observed in the A5 well drilled in 1988 immediately NW of the Fialé caldera, with the hydrothermal mineral sequence matching the resistivity profile but not the temperature, showing a late inflow of cold sea water which in fact maintained the cooling as feared by Varet (2014)

6. LTFZ: LEAKY TRANSFORM FAULT ZONE

From investigations of Kenyan and Ethiopian geothermal sites, Varet et al. (2020) could show that, in the leaky transform fault zones (LTFZ), where magma differentiation at shallow depth allowed for the development of silicic units, particularly promising large size geothermal systems can be identified (Fig.11). This is notably the case at Era Boru, where an accommodation zone allows to transfer the spreading segment from the Alayta axial range north to the Manda Hararo range.

Fig. 11 Left: Location of Era Boru (EB) in CNR-CNRS Afar maps. The basement discontinuities (bottom of faulted escarpment) underlined in dark brown; spreading axis of axial ranges (Erta Ale, Alayta and Manda Harraro) in red; transverse volcano-tectonic structures in violet. Central image: plate tectonic interpretation with Fracture Zone (FZ) and Transform Fault (TF). Right: Geological map of Dabbahu characterized by peralkaline obsidians (yellow) topping a shield volcano made of basalts (blue) and intermediate lava (mugearite, dark trachyte, violet).

On a plateau, 5x3 Km wide, 700m high, at the foot of the Dabbahu volcano (studied in depth by Barberi et al., 1975), given the numerous steam vents engineered by the Afar local pastoralists (Fig.12), a study allowed to define a more restricted target (one square Km) for the Geothermal Village project, aiming to provide both Energy and water for local use (the area is off-grid). This as a first step before large developments of national interest will be considered.

Fig. 12: Within the whole Era Boru area, steam – well visible early morning - is leaking all along faults and silicic domes (top). Typical view of steam vent along a fault zone and artisanal wells engineered by Afar people to condensate the steam for liquid water production. Given the long-lasting extensive exploitation of the Steam, Gardo & Varet (2020) described there a “geothermal civilisation”.

Note that, in central Afar the Tendaho graben, extending south from Manda Harraro, can also be seen as a wide accommodation zone i.e. LTFZ between the Manda Harraro, Manda Inakir and Asal axial ranges (Barberi & Varet, 1975; 1977). Mainly filled by recent sedimentary deposits from the Awash and Mille rivers, the area is also affected by a few recent volcanic units, and several hydrothermal sites, two of them – Dubte and Alelobad chosen as targets for geothermal development, by the Federal Ethiopian Government.

7 SAMA : SOUTHERN AFAR MER AXIS

In southern Afar, along the MER axis, 7 central volcanoes display series of differentiated products, including ignimbrites, calderas, and associated hydrothermal systems potentially suitable for geothermal developments (Fig.13 Left). The northernmost is Gabilema, which is also affected by the southern fault margin of the Tendaho graben The southernmost is Fantale, at the southern extremity of the Afar Regional state.

At present, surface exploration is engaged by private investors at Fantale and Dofan, the two southernmost sites, nearer to the Addis Ababa – Djibouti communication and development axis. Fantale is a complex strato-volcano, which gave an important sequence of lava flows and pyroclastics with a huge ignimbrite eruption that’s shape the surrounding relief and all the rift floor. Made of

peralkaline rhyolite, it lies very flat all around the volcano up to large distances and is known for its “blisters” crossed by the Addis-Ababa – Djibouti railway. The magma types erupted from Fantale varies from basalts to pantellerites with all intermediate products.

Fig.13: Left: relief map of the seismic and volcanic activity in the Afar part of the MER. In red, the active volcanic segments in Afar, where best geothermal resource are located. The grey circles show the most important seismic events in the period 1960-2009 Centre: geological map showing the 3 northernmost volcanic units of the SAMA play type (same legend as above). Right: satellite image of the Fantale volcano, caldera and surrounding ignimbrite cover.

Culminating at 2.007 m, Fantale is dominating by 1.000 m the surrounding plains. Its truncated shape results from the presence of a well-expressed elliptical (3.5x2.5 Km) summit caldera elongated WNW-ESE which top the edifice (Fig.13 right). It exhibits steep walls, 200 to 250 m high, with a floor at 1.465 m. The last (historical: 1810-1830) eruptions were made of scoriaceous basalts giving rise to cones and flows at the south flank of the volcano. The presence of hyaloclastite cones shows the magma-water interaction that developed at shallow depth. Numerous normal faults of NNE-SSW direction and associated flows, affecting the last ignimbrite sheet and even more recent volcanic features show the active distensive rift axis crossing through this recent volcanic unit. Several hot-springs are observed north and south of the volcano, and fumaroles within and around the caldera walls. Garnets of hydrothermal origin were described by Varet (1969).

8. AFAF: AFAR FLOOR ACTIVE FAULTS

Along the Afar floor, active faults affecting the stratoid series (3 to 1 My ; Barberi et al., 1972) and even tiny indication of alteration along open fissures mark the widespread crypto-geothermal activity prevailing below the dry apparently desertic surface. These manifestations result from strong stress fields and deformation of microplates between spreading axis (Barberi & Varet, 1977; Manighetti et al., 2001. Fig.14).

Fig.14 Left : microplate interpretation of Afar by Barberi & Varet (1977) showing the rotation and consequent deformation of Central Afar microplate. Right : Tectonic scheme by Manighetti et al. (1996) showing block tearing as a result of rotation. L is initial block length; as blocks are fixed at both extremities, they need to tear to compensate the "length decrease (AL)" that results from their rotation by angle. Faults in the tear zone are not rotated and strike perpendicular to regional direction of extension.

The surface manifestations allow for local energy and water production systems based on exploitation of steam surface upwelling (Fig.15). The condensation is operated by local pastors in chimneys built from surrounding basalt blocks, with the efficiency of the system eventually improved by cementation. This indicates that small-size geothermal devices could be developed more widely even in these apparently bared surfaces, through geo-scientific investigations which were never engaged yet.

In Djibouti Republic, all sites drilled for water in the western part of the country, that is within this part of Afar affected by the deformations described in Fig.14, encountered anomalous heat conditions which obliged to abandon the well. The whole area, covered by the faulted stratoid series but deprived of recent volcanic unit, could be considered as a target of wide geothermal interest. Further research may help identify larger size development perspective trough drilling fractured objectives at depth in this wide area, extending both in the Ethiopian Afar Reginal State and in Djibouti.

Fig. 15 Left & Centre: At Elidaar in central Afar, along an open fissure cutting through the Stratoid series, from which the steam surge, producing clay alteration products as well as carbonate and silica deposits, a set of water condensators are built for drinking water collection, and washing/bathing, made available for nomads passing nearby (Photos J. Varet). Right: Geological map of the area (Varet, 1975; Varet & Gasse, 1978) showing the intensively faulted stratoid series (green) and the location of the Elidaar site (red dot)

9. DAMA ALE A UNIQUE CASE

A rather specific geothermal play type is found near the Ethio-Djibouti border, with the hydrothermally active Dama Ale shield volcano, built at the intersection between the Red Sea – Aden rift (Tendaho-Gobaad rift segment, WNW-ESE) and the MER (NNE-SSW) at the extremity of the Awash Valley endoreic basin (ending at Lake Abhé, Fig.16). The site displays all the characteristics of a high temperature geothermal system with a well-developed magma chamber (providing a complete set of lava from basalts to rhyolite, with all intermediate product), with a set of silicic domes showing the surface expression of a cone sheet, and a summit caldera from which a pumice eruption affected the surrounding plains (and notably the Lake Abhé surroundings) a few thousand years ago. The site was recommended by Varet (2020) for a bilateral Ethio-Djiboutian project, as it sits along the border.

While surface exploration was engaged on the eastern side of the lake by the Djiboutian Public Entity in charge (ODDEG), with the support from Iceland Aid Program and more recently in the frame of the LEAP-RE Geothermal Village project (Geraud et al., 2022), the site offers perspectives for larger size development including electricity production at Eastern and Southern foot of Dama Ale Volcano.

CONCLUSION

Afar may be considered as a single geothermal target, quite specific and valuable due to its unique geodynamic and geographic environment. It should be considered as a major target of planetary interest for the future geothermal developments needed to answer the climate change challenge. A systematic inventory of the geothermal resources allows to distinguish these 8 play types which characterize the resource and determine the usage. Except for the artisanal devices locally engineered for water condensation from steam, or direct uses of hot-springs for bathing, washing and herds watering, no

geothermal development was successfully engaged in Afar yet, despite promising resources. It is hoped that this contribution will help for the development of this huge and diversified resource, implying both public policies and human resource as well as international partnerships in science, technology, finance and industry. An appropriate approach, taking into account the diversity of the Afar geothermal play types should allow to engage solutions of resilience of local communities and national interest in this area which is not only severely affected by climate change, but offers solutions of planetary interest.

Fig.16: Left: Geological map of Dama Ale volcano (from J.Varet, CNR-CNRS, 1975). This rather symmetrical dominantly basaltic shield volcano sits at the connection of the NNW-SSE Tendaho Graben with the WNW-ESE Gobaad graben. The resulting dominant trend is NW-SE as observed in the numerous normal faults affecting the basaltic Statoid Series (3 to 1 My old, Barberi et al., 1972). The NNE-SSW trending Main Ethiopian Rift (MER) northern end is well visible South of the volcano. This central volcano, an exception within Afar recent quaternary units was certainly generated due to the combined effect of Red-Sea – Aden oceanic rift and MER continental rift (reaching 7mm/y at this northern extremity). Right: the basaltic crater surrounded by the caldera collapse following the pumice eruption which also emitted plutonic blocks sampling the underlying geological sequence (Varet, 2018). Main Hydrothermal manifestations are reported on the map, as well as the limits of the area recommended for the geothermal study on both sides of the border (crossing Abhé Bad N-S).

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REFERENCES

- Barberi, F. & Varet, J., (1970). The Erta `Ale volcanic range. *Bull. Volc.*, 34, 848- 917.
- Barberi, F., Borsi, S., Ferrara, G., Marinelli, G. & Varet, J., (1970). Relations between tectonics and magmatology in the northern Danakil Depression (Ethiopia). *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, A267, 293 - 311.
- Barberi, F., Tazieff, H. & Varet, J., (1972). Volcanism in the Afar depression: its tectonic and magmatic significance, *Tectonophysics*, 15, 19–29.
- Barberi, F., S. Borsi, G. Ferrara, G. Marinelli, R. Santacroce, H. Tazieff & J. Varet (1972) Evolution of the Danakil Depression (Afar Ethiopia) in light of radiometric age determination, *Journal of Geology* 80, pp. 720–729.
- Barberi, F., Cheminee, J. L. & Varet, J., (1973). Long-lived lava lakes of Erta Ale volcano. *Revue de Geographie Physique et de Geologie Dynamique*, 15, 347 - 352.

- Barberi, F., Bonatti, E., Marinelli, G., & Varet, J. (1974). Transverse tectonics during the split of a continent: data from the Afar rift. *Tectonophysics*, 23, 17-19.
- Barberi, F., G. Ferrara, R. Santacroce, M. Treuil & J. Varet, (1975). A transitional basalt-pantellerite sequence of fractional crystallisation, the Boina centre (Afar rift, Ethiopia), *J. Petrol.* 16, pp. 22–56.
- Barberi, F. & Varet, J., (1977). Volcanism in Afar: small-scale plate tectonic implications, *Bull. Geol. Soc. Amer.*, 88, 1251–1266.
- Bosworth, W., Huchon, P., McClay, K. (2005) The Red Sea and Gulf of Aden basins *Journal of African Earth Sciences* 43(1): 334-378
- CNR-CNRS (also quoted Barberi F., Giglia G., Marrineli G., Santacroce R. Tazieff H., and Varet J. Carte géologique du Nord de l’Afar, CNRS-CNR à 1/500 000^e (1971).
- Dobre, C., Peltzer, G., Mohamed, K., Deprez, A., Socquet, A., Masson, F.: Dynamics of opening at the western tip of the Aden Ridge: insight from geodetic and seismic data. Magmatic Rifting and Active Volcanism. *Abstract. Afar Rift Consortium. Addis Abeba* (2012) p.111.
- Duffield, WA, Bullen, TD; Clynne, MA; Fournier RO, Janik CJ, Lanphere MA, Lowenstern J, Smith JG, Giorgis L, Kahsai G, Mariam K, Tesfai T. “Geothermal potential of the Alid volcanic center, Danakil Depression, Eritrea.” *US Geological Survey Open File Report* 291:62 (1997)
- ELC (1987) geothermal reconnaissance study of selected geothermal sites in the Ethiopian rift System. Final report to EGS. 174p.
- Gardo I.A. & Varet, J. (2020) A Geothermal Civilization in the Afar Region: Era Boru (Teru woreda, Ethiopia) *Proceedings, 8th African Rift Geothermal Conference Nairobi, Kenya: November 2020* 14p
- Goitom, B., Oppenheimer, C., Hammond, J.O.S. *et al.* “First recorded eruption of Nabro volcano, Eritrea, 2011”. *Bull Volcanol* (2015) 77, 85.
- Haga, A. O., Youssouf, S.K. & Varet, J. (2012): The Manda-Inakir geothermal prospect area, Djibouti Republic. *Proceedings of the 4th African Rift Geothermal Conference. Nairobi, Kenya, November 2012*, 7p.
- Haga, A. O., Cheik, H. S. & Varet, J. (2012): The Obock and Rouéli geothermal sites, Djibouti Republic. *Proceedings of the 4th African Rift Geothermal Conference. Nairobi, Kenya, 21-23 November 2012*, 9p.
- Hamlyn, J. E., Keir, D., Wright, T. J., Neuberg, J. W., Goitom, B., Hammond JOS (2014). Seismicity and subsidence following the 2011 Nabro eruption, Eritrea: Insights into the plumbing system of an off-rift volcano. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 119 (11), 8267–8282.
- Hamling, I., Ayele, A., Bennati, L., Calais, E., Ebinger, C., Keir, D., ... Yirgu, G. (2009). Geodetic observations of the ongoing Dabbahu rifting episode: New dyke intrusions in 2006 and 2007. *Geophysical Journal International*, 178(2), 989–1003.
- Hammond, J., Kendall, J.-M., Stuart, G., Ebinger, C., Bastow, I., Keir, D., ... Wright, T. J. (2013). Mantle upwelling and initiation of rift segmentation beneath the Afar Depression. *Geology*, 41(6), 635–638.
- Houmed, A. M., Haga, A. O. Abdilahi, S. & Varet, J. (2012): Nord-Ghoubbet geothermal site, Djibouti Republic. *Proceedings of the 4th African Rift Geothermal Conference. Nairobi, Kenya, 7p.*
- Houmed, A. M., Haga, A. O. Abdilahi, S. & Varet, J. (2012) : Proposal for new geothermal models and sites hierarchy in Djibouti Republic. *Proceedings of the 4th African Rift Geothermal Conference. Nairobi, Kenya, 21-23 November 2012*, 10p.
- Houmed, A. M., Haga, A. O. Abdilahi, S. & Varet, J. (2012): The Asal geothermal site, Djibouti Republic (model update, 2012), *Proceedings of the 4th African Rift Geothermal Conference. Nairobi, Kenya, 21-23 November 2012*, 9p.
- Houmed, A. M., Haga, A. O. & Varet, J. (2012): A revised approach to the Hanlé-Gaggadé (Djibouti Republic): the Garabbayis geothermal site. *Proceedings of the 4th African Rift Geothermal Conference. Nairobi, Kenya, 21-23 November 2012*, 7p.
- Keir, D., Hamling, I.J., Ayele, A., Calais, E., Ebinger, C., Wright, T.J., Jacques, E., Mohamed, K., Hammond, J.O.S., Belachew, M., Baker, E., Rowland, J.V., Lewi, E., Rowland, J.V., Lewi, E., Bennati, L., 2009. Evidence for focused magmatic accretion at segment centres from lateral dike injections beneath the Red Sea rift in Afar. *Geology* 37,
- Keir, D., C. Pagli, I. D. Bastow, and A. Ayele (2011), The magma-assisted removal of Arabia in Afar: Evidence from dike injection in the Ethiopian rift captured using InSAR and seismicity, *Tectonics*, 30,

- Manighetti, I., P. Tapponnier, V. Courtillot, S. Gruszow, and P.-Y. Gillot (1997), Propagation of rifting along the Arabia-Somalia plate boundary: The gulfs of Aden and Tadjoura, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 102, 2681–2710.
- Manighetti, I., Tapponnier, P., Courtillot, V., Gallet, Y., Jacques, E. & Gillot P.-Y.: Strain transfer between disconnected, propagating rifts in Afar. *J. Geophys. Res.* (2001) 106, B7, p.13613-13661
- Pagli, C., Wright, T.J., Ebinger, C.J., Yun, S.-H., Cann, J.R., Barnie, T. & Ayele, A., 2012. Shallow axial magma chamber at the slow-spreading Erta Ale Ridge, *Nat. Geosci.*, 5, 284–288.
- Souleiman, H., Houmed, A. M., Khaireh, A. Haga, A. O., Abdillahi, S. O., Aye F. (2012): Geothermal Development in Djibouti Republic: A Country Report. *Proceedings of the 4th African Rift Geothermal Conference . Nairobi, Kenya, 21-23 November 2012*, 7p.
- UN Mission report (1973): Project Ethiopia/78/007-Development of geothermal resources, 469p.
- Varet J. (1969) - New discovery of fumarolitic garnets (Fant'Ale, Ethiopia). *Contrib. Mineral Petrol.*, 22, 185-189.
- Varet J. (1975) - Carte géologique de l'Afar central et méridional, *CNR-CNRS, 1/500 000 Géotechnip*.
- Varet, J. (2014): Asal-Fialé geothermal field (Djibouti republic): A new interpretation for a geothermal reservoir in an actively spreading rift segment. *Proceedings 5th African Rift geothermal Conference, Arusha, Tanzania, 29-31 October 2014*
- Varet, J. (2018) Geology of Afar (East Africa) *Ed. Springer*. 1st ed., 397 p., 377 illus.
- Varet, J. (2018) Geothermal resource along the border: The Ethiopia-Djibouti case. *Proceedings, 7th African Rift Geothermal Conference Kigali, Rwanda 31st October – 2nd November 2018*. 14 p.
- Varet, J. (2020). Geothermal for Peace: Exploration and development of the large Bidu-Dubbi geothermal prospect along the border of Ethiopia and Eritrea. *Proceedings, 8th African Rift Geothermal Conference Nairobi, Kenya: 2 – 8 November 2020*, 13p.
- Varet, J. (2022) African Geothermal Play Types; Typology for Identification ; Development Approach. *Proceedings, 9th African Rift Geothermal Conference, Djibouti, 3rd 5th Nov. 2022*, 17p.
- Varet, J. & Gardo. I.A. (2020) Another geothermal site in North-Eastern Afar: Harak (Bidu woreda, Afar regional state, Ethiopia), that marks the southernmost extension of the Danakil Sea 110m bsl *Proceedings, 8th African Rift Geothermal Conference Nairobi, Kenya: 2 – 8 November 2020*, 13p.
- Varet J. & Gasse F. (1978) - Geology of central and meridional Afar. *Ed. CNRS*, 140 p
- Viltres R. Jonsson S., Ruch J., Doubre C., Reilinger, R., Floyd, M. & Ogubazghi, G. (2020) Kinematics and deformation of the southern Red Sea region from GPS observations *Geophys. J. Int.* (2020) 221, 2143–2154
- Wondifra, T., Yismaw, A., Kebede, Y., Abdulahid, T. & Mengesha, K (2022) Geothermal Exploration Using Magnetotelluric (Mt) & Gravity Methods At Arabi, Somali Regional State North-East, Ethiopia And its Geothermal Implications. *Proceedings, 9th African Rift Geothermal Conference Djibouti, 3rd November – 5th November 2022*
- Wright, T.J., Ebinger, C.J., Biggs, J., Ayele, A., Yirgu, G., Keir, D., and Stork, A., “Magma maintained rift segmentation at continental rupture in the 2005 Afar dyking episode” *Nature*. 442, 291–294 (2006)
- Yohannes, E. (2012) Geothermal Development in Eritrea: A Country Update *Proceedings 4th African Rift Geothermal Conference Nairobi, Kenya, 21-23 November 2012*
- Zwaan, F., Corti, G., Sani, F., Keir, D., Muluneh, A. A., Illsley-Kemp, F., & Papini, M. (2020). Structural analysis of the Western Afar Margin, East Africa: Evidence for multiphase rotational rifting. *Tectonics*, 39.